

Andreoff Project, Wyandot County (40.75722, -83.49430)

Since construction in 2022, the Andreoff Project has functioned as an isolated wetland at which periods of increased rainfall can cause surface runoff from the surrounding fields to drain into the pool, which then drains into an adjacent ditch when it reaches maximum capacity. However, this intermittent outflow has only been qualitatively observed by researchers and would require drainage area calculations and the installation of a flume to accommodate collection of outflow samples to assess the Project's nutrient filtration function. The main depressional pool retains water during most of the year even under prolonged drought conditions.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 278 acres of restored wetland and consists of a single 1.5-acre wetland pool without designed inflows or outflows. The pool receives surface runoff from the surrounding landscape and largely functions as an isolated wetland. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as an event where the site receives runoff.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar isolated wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Installing a flume or a water level control structure would allow water to exit the Main Pool at a set location and give researchers a set point to determine the nutrient concentration at this intermittent outflow.
- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.